

PRESTRESS LOSS MONITORING OF NEAR-SURFACE MOUNTED CFRP STRIPS EMBEDDED IN CONCRETE BASED ON OFBG SENSORS

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1. Introduction

In recent years, optical fiber (OF) based sensing techniques have been applied to monitor prestress loss in prestressed concrete due to their excellent performance, such as corrosion resistance, high durability, high accuracy, electro-magnetic resistance, quasi-distribution, and absolute measurement [1-3]. Watkins employed the Fabry-Perot interferometric sensor to measure the internal strain in the main load-carrying layers [4]. Idriss et al. installed 2m long gauge optical fiber deformation sensors into concrete girders of the Rio Puerco and I-10 Bridge over a University in Las Cruces in order to evaluate the in-situ material properties, prestress losses and cambers in the girders [5]. Xuan et al. installed 14 fiber-optic sensors on the steel strand through the pre-designed window on a sewage-treating tank [6], to monitor and quantitatively evaluate the prestress losses in the steel-strand reinforced concrete structures. Zhou et al. integrated the optical fiber sensors into fiber-reinforced polymer rebars for their improved ruggedness, and then used these smart FRP rebars for cables and steel strands to monitor the in-service long-term stress conditions. Their results indicated that the smart FRP rebars had good compatibility with the steel strands in both mechanical and sensing properties [7].

As a type of OF sensor, the Optical Fiber Bragg grating (OFBG) sensor has been widely accepted as a novel non-destructive evaluation (NDE) technique in monitoring strain and temperature profiles of structures under service conditions [8]. In recent years, a number of researchers have focused on the application aspect of the OFBG-based method in FRP composite materials and structures, including but not limited to: FRP hardening process monitoring, FRP-OFBG smart materials and structures using FRP bars, plates and cables, and other FRP reinforced or strengthened structures [9-11].

Nowadays, rehabilitation of deficient structures has

become an important topic increasingly attracting research attention. Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP) composites have been more and more used as effective rehabilitation materials in this field. The advantages of FRP materials over traditional materials such as concrete or steel include the high corrosion resistance, light weight, high specific strength and stiffness, low maintenance costs [12,13].

The use of FRPs in structural rehabilitation, such as the externally bonded method, has been extensively researched in lots of literature. However, the prevalent debonding failure still remains an issue for this method. The near-surface mounted (NSM) method, on the other hand, has shown promising improvements in this type of failure as well as increasing the flexural and shear strength of the concrete members [14,15]. The prestressing concept has also been applied to this technique to more efficiently utilize the high strength of the composite materials, using methods such as gradient, hydraulic jacking and external post-tensioning [16,17]. In addition, prestressing is found to further improve the serviceability condition of the structure by decreasing the deflection under service loads and preventing or delaying the crack formation and propagation in concrete. However, the effectiveness of the prestressed NSM technique is still limited by the constructability in the field and especially the amount of short-term and long-term prestress losses in the system. How to reliably monitor these losses for precise control of prestress application to meet the design expectation is a challenging issue.

In this paper, the OFBG technique is applied to monitor the prestress losses and damage propagation in a series of reinforced concrete beams strengthened with NSM CFRP strips pre-tensioned by a newly developed prestressing device. The NSM strips were prestressed to various levels of stress and the flexural capacities of the beams were obtained by performing four-point bending tests. Bare OFBG

sensors were installed directly on the surface of the NSM CFRP strips that were then embedded in the concrete. The results showed that the OFBG-based sensing technique was effective in accurately capturing the short-term prestress losses during the construction as well as the time-dependent long-term losses. It also provided a qualitative method in detecting initial damages and crack propagation in the concrete under loading conditions.

2. FRP-OFBG smart materials

2.1 Techniques of Encapsulated OFBG with FRP materials

There are two typical methods to integrate the OFBG sensors into the FRP materials for monitoring purpose. One is to embed the OFBG inside of the FRP materials during the manufacturing process such as wet lay-up and pultrusion, as illustrated in Figure 1. The other method is to bond the OFBG sensors on the surface of the FRP reinforcement or prepreg using adhesives such as resin, with or without cuts on the FRP surface. Figure 2 shows such an example for the NSM FRP type of reinforcement, where bare OFBG sensors are directly bonded onto the NSM CFRP strips.

Fig.1 OFBG embedded inside CFRP laminate during wet lay-up

Fig.2 OFBG bonded on the surface of the NSM CFRP strip

2.2 Strain transfer theory of FRP-OFBG smart materials

Because of the existence of the adhesive layer when bonding OFBG sensors to the substrate, difference can be caused between the strain measurement by the OFBG sensors and the actual strain changes in the substrate (host) material. Therefore, the strain measurements by the OFBG sensors need to be

modified using strain transfer theories. According to the model proposed by Ou and Li [18], when OFBG is bonded to the surface of any host material, the interface strain transfer error rate(η) can be estimated by Eq. (1) and the modification coefficient (k) is obtained by Eq. (2) as:

$$\eta = \frac{|\bar{\varepsilon}_c - \bar{\varepsilon}_h|}{\bar{\varepsilon}_h} = \frac{\cosh(\lambda l_f) - 1}{\lambda l_f \cdot \sinh(\lambda l_f)} \quad (1)$$

$$k = \frac{1}{1 - \eta} \quad (2)$$

Where ε_c is the strain of OFBG, ε_h is the practical strain of the host materials, λ is the eigenvalue and l_f is the length of the bare OFBG sensor.

The elastic modulus of epoxy resin has a typical range of 2 GPa to 20 GPa [19,20]. Based on the mechanics of materials basics, the shear modulus (G) can be calculated from the elastic modulus (E) and the Poisson's ration (γ), i.e.,

$$G = \frac{E}{2(1 + \gamma)} \quad (3)$$

Hence, the shear modulus ranges from 0.77 GPa to 7.69 GPa with the Poisson's ratio value of 0.3. The elastic modulus of the OFBG sensor is typically about 70 GPa and the length of the OFBG sensor is 10mm. Based on these properties, the error rate (η) can be obtained in terms of the shear modulus (G) and the thickness of the adhesive layer (h), as illustrated in Figure 3 and Figure 4. The modification coefficient (k) can then be calculated using Eq. (2).

Fig.3 Effect of shear module on the strain transfer error coefficient

Fig.4 Effect of adhesive layer thickness on the strain transfer error coefficient

From Figure 3, one can see that the error rate decreases as the shear modulus increases. The error rate increases as the thickness of adhesive layer increases. Theoretically, a thin adhesive layer is desired when bonding the OFBG sensors to CFRP if similar strain changes are expected to those in the conventional electrical strain gauges. The strain changes of the NSM CFRP strips can then be obtained using the modification coefficient (k) from Eq. (2) as:

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_h = k \cdot \bar{\varepsilon}_c \quad (4)$$

In this study, the shear modulus(G)of the adhesive used for bonding OFBG and CFRP strips is about 1.15GPa, and the adhesive layer thickness (h) is about 0.6mm. The error rate (η) and the modification coefficient (k) are thus calculated to be 0.052 and 1.055, respectively.

2.3 Analysis of prestress loss

Due to the small size of the OFBG sensor, its deformation can be assumed to be the same as that of a single fiber. According to the strain transfer theory previously discussed, the strain of the NSM CFRP strip can be easily obtained. Based on the Hook's law, the stress of the CFRP strip is calculated from the strain measured by the OFBG sensor, i.e.,

$$\sigma = \frac{E_i}{\alpha_\varepsilon} \Delta\lambda_B = \frac{E_i}{1.2k} \Delta\lambda_B \quad (5)$$

Where σ is the stress of the CFRP strip, E_i is the elastic module of the CFRP strip, $\Delta\lambda_B$ is the change of central wavelength of the OFBG sensor, and α_ε is the modified strain sensitivity coefficient of the OFBG sensor, which typically equals to the modification coefficient (k) times the original strain

sensitivity coefficient of the OFBG sensor (i.e., $1.2 \text{ pm}/\mu\varepsilon$).

Prestress loss is essentially the decrease of the initial prestressing force in the CFRP strips. It typically consists of two parts: the instantaneous short-term loss and the time-dependent long-term loss. The instantaneous loss occurs immediately after the release of the CFRP strips from the anchors and can be due to friction during the post-tensioning, anchorage settlement at the end of the prestressed CFRP strips, and the elastic shortening in concrete. The time-dependent loss occurs more slowly over the life span of the prestressed structure and it includes the losses due to CFRP strips relaxation, creep and shrinkage of the bonding agent and concrete. Since the CFRP material behaves linear elastically, the Young's modulus of the material (E_i) is a constant. In addition, the strain sensitivity coefficient of the OFBG sensor (α_ε) is a constant. Therefore, the total prestress loss can be obtained through monitoring the strain level in the OFBG sensors, i.e., the change of central wavelength of the OFBG sensor ($\Delta\lambda_B$).

3. Experiment of monitoring prestress loss

3.1 Materials

Figure 5 illustrates the OFBG monitoring system used in this study. The bare OFBG sensors used have a central wavelength changing scale larger than 10000 pm and a gauge length of 15mm. The strain and temperature sensing coefficients of the sensor are $1.2 \text{ pm}/\mu\varepsilon$ and $10 \text{ pm}/^\circ\text{C}$, respectively. The Micron Optics OFBG interrogator used has 4 channels with a scanning frequency of 50Hz and the wavelength range is about 1510—1590 nm.

Fig.5 OFBG monitoring system

The NSM CFRP strips are 16 mm wide and 4.5 mm thick with a roughened surface condition. The mechanical properties of the CFRP strips are listed in Table 1, with the data provided by the manufacturer and obtained from laboratory tests per ACI 440.3R-04 [21]. The bonding agent is Sikadur 32 epoxy, which is a 2-component, 100% solids and moisture-tolerant structural epoxy adhesive. The

mechanical properties of the adhesive per manufacturer’s data are shown in Table 2. The average 28-day compressive strength of the normal

weight concrete is tested as 28.9 MPa per ASTM C39 [22].

Table 1 Properties of NSM CFRP strips

Size (mm)	Sectional area (mm ²)	Source	Elastic modulus (GPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Tensile strain (%)
16×4.5	71.3	Manufacturer	124.00	1,965.00	1.50
		Laboratory	124.51	1,675.82	1.42

Table 2 Mechanical properties of the adhesive

Test	Value	ASTM test method
Tensile strength (MPa)	48	D638
Tensile modulus (GPa)	3.726	D638
Elongation at break (%)	1.90	D638
Flexural strength (MPa)	48.3	D790
Flexural modulus (GPa)	4.8	D790
Shear strength (MPa)	43	D732
Bond strength (MPa)	13.8	C882

3.2 Setup configuration

Eight 1.37 m long concrete beam specimens were constructed, where each specimen had a rectangular cross-sectional dimension of 152 mm wide and 203 mm high (i.e., 6×8 in). These beams were designed as conventional steel reinforced concrete beams per ACI 318-08 [23]. Two control specimens (C-A and C-B) strengthened with non-prestressed NSM reinforcement was constructed for comparison purpose. For the strengthened beams, one NSM CFRP strip was embedded at the bottom surface of the concrete, where a 28.5 mm deep and 25 mm wide groove was cut first. Figure 6 illustrates the overall cross-sectional dimension and the reinforcement details of the beams. To monitor the prestress loss and strain levels, two bare OFBG sensors were bonded on one side of the flat surfaces of the CFRP strip near the center and quarter length (corresponding to the mid-span and quarter-span location of the beam). For comparison purpose, two

conventional electrical strain gauges were also installed at the same locations along the length but on the opposite side of the flat surfaces, as shown in Figure 7.

Fig.6 Beam cross-section

Fig.7 OFBG sensors and strain gauges bonded on the NSM CFRP strips

Three prestressing levels were designed for the 6 NSM strengthened beams: 10%, 15%, and 20% (2 specimens per each category, i.e., C-10, C-15 and C-20). These desired prestressing levels corresponded to the percent of the ultimate tensile strain of the CFRP strip (i.e., 1.42% based on the laboratory data). The amount of prestressing force needed for each case was then achieved by monitoring the strain measurements from the electrical gauges and OFBG sensors. Once the desired prestressing level was reached, epoxy resin was poured into the pre-cut grooves up to the concrete top surface, as shown in Figure 8. The prestress losses of each beam were then closely monitored for 6 consecutive days before the load testing.

Fig.8 Pouring epoxy into the grooves

3.3 Results on prestress loss

The prestressing device used in the study was previously developed by Lee and Cheng [24] to provide an easy and economical NSM prestressing method for field applications. The unit consists of two tubular steel sleeves slides outside the two ends of the NSM strip (filled with epoxy adhesive in the gap) and two anchorage rings at the far ends. At one end, the steel sleeve is welded to the anchorage ring cut from a large steel tube forming an eyebolt shape. At the other end, the steel sleeve is welded to a threaded rod that is then connected to the anchorage ring using a nut and a washer (Figure 9). To minimize the rotation of the sleeve during prestressing, a small steel disc is welded to the outside of the sleeve inside the groove. To host the anchorage rings, two round holes are pre-drilled on the bottom surface of concrete in addition to the groove using a concrete

core drill. After the entire unit is positioned in the middle of the slot, a prestressing force is applied by hand tightening the nut using a wrench, as shown in Figure 10.

Fig.9 Illustration for the prestressing unit

Fig.10 Applying prestressing force

Beam specimen C-20-B was first prestressed up to 20% (design level) quickly followed by epoxy pouring inside the groove. Shortly after this, the strain level in the CFRP strip showed a sudden drop from 2840 $\mu\epsilon$ to 1770 $\mu\epsilon$, and which was about 42.3% loss in 12 hours, as measured by OFBG. This initial loss was unexpectedly high. Therefore, the prestressing force was applied more carefully to the remaining beams prior to filling the grooves with epoxy. The modified monitoring data by the modification coefficient (k) based on OFBG during the first 12 hours after groove filling is shown in Figure 12a and 12b. It can be seen that beam specimen C-20-A experienced a 38.2% prestress loss. Specimens C-10-A and C-10-B had a prestress loss of 34.0% and 27.8%, respectively. C-15-A and C-15-B experienced a 44.5% and 50% prestressing loss, respectively.

The complete set of monitoring data on the prestress loss from the OFBG sensors is shown in Figure 11 for both mid-span and quarter-span. After the initial 12 hours, the monitoring of the prestress loss was continued for another 6 days before the load testing of the specimens. It can be seen that after the initial loss, the strain level inside the CFRP strips began to stabilize. For the 10% prestressed beams, the strain at the end of the 6-day period in C-10-A decreased from the initial 1025.6 $\mu\epsilon$ to 379.7 $\mu\epsilon$ and that in C-10-B

changed from 1785.8 $\mu\epsilon$ to 1146.9 $\mu\epsilon$, corresponding to a prestress loss of 63.0% and 35.8%, respectively. Beams C-15-A and C-15-B had a 41.4% and 40.0% prestress loss, respectively. Beams C-20-A and C-20-B had a loss of 44.0% and 53.1%, respectively. It can also be seen that, in general, the prestress losses at the quarter-span is slightly higher than that at the mid-span.

Fig.11 Prestressing losses in CFRP strip monitored by OFBG at: (a) mid-span, and (b) quarter-span

The prestress losses measured by the OFBG sensors are further confirmed by the use of conventional strain gauges. It also can be seen that certain difference exists between the data obtained from the OFBG sensors and the conventional strain gauges, as shown in Figure 12. This was likely caused by the existence of the additional torsional moment introduced by hand tightening the nut on the anchorage ring at one end of the prestressing unit.

Fig.12 Comparison of prestress losses from OFBGs and strain gauges over: (a) initial 12 hours immediately after prestressing, and (b) over 6 days after prestressing

Using Eq. (4), the actual strain difference in the CFRP strips can be obtained by multiplying the strain values from the OFBG sensors by the modification coefficient (k). The resulting prestress losses in the CFRP strips can then be calculated from the modified strain difference using Eq. (5). Figure 13 compares the prestress losses after the initial 12 hours (12h) and

at the end of the 6-day monitoring period (6d). It can be seen that at the end of the 6-day period, the maximum amount of prestress loss reached 141.81MPa in beam C-20-A and the minimum was 80MPa in beam C-10-A.

Fig.13 Comparison of prestressing losses from OFBGs after initial 12 hours and 6 days

4. Experiment of beam bending test

4.1 Specimens and test setup

All beam specimens were tested under a 4-point bending configuration at the end of the 6-day monitoring period. The beams were simply supported at the ends and the deflection of the beam was measured using linear potentiometers (LPs) at both the mid-span and the quarter-span. The strain levels in CFRP were measured by the OFBG sensors and the strain gauges. Figure 14 illustrates the overall test setup and the instrumentation plan.

Name convention: OFBG=Optical fiber bragg gratings. CSG=Concrete strain gauge. LP= Linear potentiometer

Fig.14 Beam bending test setup and instrumentation plan

4.2 Beam test results

Comparing to the control specimen (C-B), the 10% prestressed beam specimens, C-10-A and C-10-B, showed an increase of the ultimate load-carrying capacity of 24% and 6%, respectively (Table 3) [25]. Specimen C-15-A only had a 3% increase over the control specimen, and C-15-B, C-20-A and C-20-B had slightly lower capacities than the control due to

the localized failure in concrete around the anchorage zones. In addition, the maximum strain changes obtained by the OFBG sensors generally compare

well with those from the strain gages (except for C-B and C-10-A), as shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Summary of beam test results

Beam	Max load (kN)	Max strain changes during loading test		Max Displacement (mm)
		SG ($\mu\epsilon$)	OFBG ($\mu\epsilon$)	
C-B	84.1	4160	2900	N/A
C-10-A	104.6	4116	3308	13.2
C-10-B	89.4	3078	2784	8.9
C-15-A	86.8	2444	2493	9.4
C-15-B	76.1	2404	1982	14.0
C-20-A	75.7	2527	2386	7.9
C-20-B	76.1	1252	1043	27.4

Figure 15 shows the representative time history of the strain level measured in the OFBG sensors during the loading process. It can be seen that the strain in the beam had sudden changes at specific times under given loads. These sudden changes of strain actually corresponded to the location of the crack and the propagation of the damage. For example, the strain in the beam C-10-A suddenly changed at the 32nd second, when the load reached about 104.6kN, as shown in Figure 16. At that time, a large crack was actually observed in concrete near the location of the OFBG sensor (C-10-AE), as shown in the picture in Figure 16. However, the conventional strain gauges were not able to capture this sudden strain change since the monitoring frequency of electrical-based strain gauge method is limited.

Fig.15 Strain changes in CFRP strip and typical crack pattern (C-10-A)

5. Conclusions

In this paper, bare OFBG sensors are integrated into the NSM CFRP strips as a novel monitoring method to measure prestress, monitor prestress loss and

detect damages during the loading process. Although small measurement differences existed in the OFBGs and conventional strain gages due to the design of the anchorage and prestressing unit, the OFBG method was able to capture the prestress losses and detect the cracking in concrete. The following conclusions can be drawn from the current study:

- The bare OFBG sensors can be easily installed and integrated into the prestressed NSM CFRP strips or other FRP materials for monitoring purpose in the field.
- The monitoring results based on the OFBG sensors showed that this method measured an accurate trend of the instantaneous prestress loss and also the time-dependent long-term prestress losses.
- The strain response by the OFBG sensors can provide useful information on the formation of cracks (damage) in the concrete.
- The accuracy of the OFBG based method is reliable and can be used in monitoring the structural response under external loading conditions.

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